

Machine learning based Freezing of Gait detection for an on-demand cueing system

V. Waldheim^{1*}, A. Dvorani^{1,2}, M. C. E. Jochner³, C. Salchow-Hömmen³, A. Kühn³, N. Wenger³, T. Schauer^{1,2}

¹ Technische Universität Berlin, Control System Group, Berlin, Germany

² SensorStim Neurotechnology GmbH, Berlin, Germany

³ Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Klinik für Neurologie, Berlin, Germany

* Corresponding author, email: schauer@control.tu-berlin.de

Abstract: For people suffering from Parkinson's disease Freezing of Gait (FoG) is one of the most disabling symptoms. Impairment and interruptions during gait restrict activities of daily life along with a high risk of falls. For alleviating FoG symptoms and to prevent complete movement blockades, a cueing system was developed which stimulates the peroneal nerve in a gait phase synchronized manner whenever a FoG episode occurs. In this article we introduce a real-time FoG detection method based on machine learning with gait features, extracted from foot mounted inertial sensors. The results show that an AdaBoost classifier improves the accuracy by 15% compared to a threshold-based algorithm.

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I. Introduction

With more than six million affected people worldwide, Parkinson's Disease (PD) is one of the major burdens for the society and health economics [1]. The neuro-degenerative disease, during which dopamine-producing cells in the substantia nigra degenerate, leads to motor impairment. Besides tremor, rigidity and bradykinesia, Freezing of Gait (FoG) is one of the most disabling symptoms. FoG is a fluctuating symptom, which can manifest itself in different subtypes: Patients suffering from FoG walk with small, fast steps (festination), experience shuffling gait (shuffling), motoric blockades with trembling of the shank in place (shank trembling) or complete motoric blockades (akinesia) [2]. Ordinary movements like getting out of a chair, passing doorways or entering a lift, crossing roads, change directions and walking among many people can become a huge obstacle and the fear of falling even aggravate this situation [3]. Hip fractures caused by falls are often related with the entry in a nursing home or with death [4]. Additionally, patients are afraid of getting in embarrassing circumstances because of shuffling or trembling legs. Therefore, they do not only walk less but also avoid social events to not attract attention resulting in social isolation. Additionally, they can get frustrated because of their restrictions and the dependence on external aid. All these factors lead to a high probability for depression and sleep disturbances [4, 5]. FoG responds poorly to available therapeutic options such as L-Dopa treatment or deep brain stimulation [6].

In a recent publication we introduced an on-demand cueing system with an inertial measurement unit (IMU) attached to one midfoot and a stimulator sending electrical impulses to the peroneal nerve of one leg, when FoG is detected [7]. The FoG detection was threshold-based on gait parameters,

which were extracted from the IMU. The method was tested on six patients using data from both feet recorded with a commercially available IMU-measurement system [8]. In this article we present an alternative method for real-time FoG classification based on machine learning methods. The aims were to improve the accuracy of the existing classification method and to investigate whether it is possible to predict FoG symptoms before they occur.

II. Material and methods

For the machine learning approach to detect FoG symptoms the data of 20 Parkinson patients (aged 67.2 ± 8.9 , 15 male) were used. They performed 10 m walking tests, as well as FoG provoking tests, consisting of standing up from a chair, two 360° turns, passing a doorway twice and sitting down again [9]. With IMU measurements from the feet at 200 Hz (MUSCLELAB, Ergotest Innovation AS, Norway), gait features were extracted, and the gait phase (motion phases of the feet) were determined, as described in [10]. With the aid of video recordings, two experts labelled the FoG symptoms shuffling, shank trembling, festination and akinesia. Overall, the dataset consisted of 10796 motion phases, including 3616 phases labelled as FoG.

Using the Classification Learner application of MATLAB, first several classifiers were trained and tested with the gait features of both feet. The following features were considered within one step: the maximal amount of the acceleration, the maximal and minimal pitch angle, the stride length, the maximal velocity, the step duration, the absolute turn angle, the maximal and the mean absolute turn rate, as well as the decision, whether the patient turned (1) or not (0).

As reference the expert labels were grouped to two classes - class 0 for normal gait and class 1 for any FoG symptom.

An adaptive boosting classifier (AdaBoost) was selected, because of its simple implementation, low memory requirements and the good performance. The settings were changed to maximal six splits and ten decision trees, to prevent overfitting and reduce the required computing performance. A leave-one-subject-out cross-validation was applied, and accuracy, specificity and sensitivity were evaluated.

After the training with the gait parameters of the present foot motion phase (referred shortly as step in the following), also gait properties of the two previous motion phases of the same foot were added to the feature set to evaluate the possibility to predict FoG phases.

The results of the classifiers were compared to the existing threshold-based approach based on an or-combination of the GaitScore [8] and the FoG criterion (FoGc) presented by Coste et al. [11]. Whereas the GaitScore evaluates FoG based on the extrema of the pitch angle, the FoGc concentrates on the step length and frequency (cadence) of the steps.

In addition, a paired, two-sided t-test at the 5% significance level was applied on the resulting accuracies to investigate whether there is a more affected foot side.

III. Results and discussion

In [8], it was indicated that patients have a foot that is more affected by FoG than the other. The statistical test for the threshold-based method has shown that there is a significantly more affected foot with a p-value of 0.04. However, the AdaBoost classifiers performed similar for both sides, with p-values of 0.64 when trained with the present step features, 0.17 for the predicting classifier and 0.1 when the classifier was trained with features of all three steps.

The results of the classification are shown in Table 1. For each patient the side with the best accuracy was considered. It can be observed that the new classifier, trained with gait features of the present step (AdaBoost step 0), outperforms the threshold-based method regarding accuracy (+0.15) and specificity (+0.25), whereas the sensitivity decreased by 0.09.

Table 1: Performance of the AdaBoost classifiers compared to the threshold-based method

	Sens.	Spec.	Acc.
AdaBoost step 0	0.87	0.90	0.89
AdaBoost step -2 and -1	0.83	0.92	0.88
AdaBoost step -2 to 0	0.87	0.93	0.91
GaitScore + FoGc	0.96	0.63	0.74

With a feature set consisting of previous gait features only (AdaBoost step -2 and -1), a FoG prediction was built. Without information of the present step the classifier predicted 83% of the FoG steps and 92% of the normal steps. Nevertheless, it must be noted, that the majority of previous steps belongs to the same class as the present steps. The prediction of the transitions often failed. The first FoG step after normal gait was predicted in 41% of the

steps and only 31% of the first normal steps could be forecasted. However, the combination of the features of the two previous steps and the present step (AdaBoost step -2 to 0) led to a small improvement of the accuracy and specificity.

IV. Conclusions

In this article, we introduced AdaBoost classifiers to detect and predict FoG motion phases (steps) for on-demand cueing and compared their performance with an existing threshold-based method. It was shown that, in contrast to the existing method, there is no significant accuracy difference between the right and the left foot. The new classifiers outperform the existing one in accuracy and specificity, but a reliable prediction of the beginning and end of FoG symptoms is not possible with the investigated method.

The “AdaBoost step 0” classifier was chosen for subsequent implementation on the on-demand cueing system. Its accuracy is only a little below “AdaBoost step -2 to 0”, but less features need to be considered. In the future, the effects of the on-demand cueing on Parkinsonian gait will be evaluated in a clinical study.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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